

PROCESSES OF THE WORLDWIDE EXPANSION OF THE MONTESSORI METHOD

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Methodology of preschool education

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Annotation This article highlights the process by which Maria Montessori's method is employed, the emergence of early schools, and the stages of the worldwide spread of this method. The importance of the Montessori method in the development of children, its advantages, disadvantages, achievements are discussed. It should also be noted that this article contains a list of common links, but it does not contain enough corresponding quotes. Please help improve this article by making more specific quotes. The Montessori method of education is an educational method that involves children's natural interests and activities rather than formal teaching methods. Montessori's class focuses on practical learning and the development of real-world skills. It emphasizes independence and believes that children are naturally passionate about knowledge and able to start learning in a sufficiently supportive and well-prepared learning environment. It rejects some traditional achievement indicators such as assessments and tests.

Key words: Montessori, learning environment, method, method of Education, Early schools

Аннотация В данной статье освещается процесс применения метода Марии Монтессори, возникновение ранних школ и этапы мирового распространения этого метода. Обсуждается значение метода Монтессори в развитии детей, его преимущества, недостатки, достижения. Также следует отметить, что данная статья содержит список общих ссылок, но не содержит достаточного количества соответствующих цитат. Пожалуйста, помогите улучшить эту статью, приведя более конкретные цитаты. Метод обучения

Монтессори — это образовательный метод, который включает в себя естественные интересы и деятельность детей, а не формальные методы обучения. Занятия Монтессори сосредоточены на практическом обучении и развитии практических навыков. Он подчеркивает независимость и считает, что дети от природы страстно стремятся к знаниям и способны начать обучение в достаточно благоприятной и хорошо подготовленной учебной среде. Он отвергает некоторые традиционные показатели достижений, такие как оценки и тесты.

Ключевые слова: Монтессори, среда обучения, метод, метод обучения, ранние школы.

Introduction

The method was started in the early 20th century by the Italian physician Maria Montessori, who developed his theories through scientific experiments with his students; this method was used in public and private schools in many parts of the world. There are a number of practices under the non-trademark name "Montessori". Popular elements include mixed-age classes, student freedom (including the choice of their activities), long blocks of continuous working hours, specially trained teachers and prepared environments. Scientific research into the Montessori method has been largely positive, with a 2017 review noting that there is "extensive evidence" for its effectiveness.

Maria Montessori began developing her educational philosophy and methods after medical training in 1897, attending pedagogical courses at the University of Rome and studying educational theory. While attending school with a teacher, Montessori observed while visiting Rome's mental hospitals. incarcerated children needed more stimulation from the environment. In 1907, he opened his first classroom, the Casa dei Bambini, or children's home, in a multi-storey building in Rome. . From the beginning, Montessori based his work on observing children and conducting experiments with the environment, materials. , and classes available to

them. He frequently referred to his work as "scientific pedagogy". In 1901, Maria Montessori met Elis and Leopoldo Franchetti, prominent educational reformers. Maria Montessori was invited to take her first course for teachers and found the "Casa dei Bambini" in Villa Montesca, home of the Franchetti in Città di Castello. Montessori lived with the Franchetti for two years and, together with Alice Franchetti, perfected his methodology. In 1909 he documented his theories in *Il metodo della pedagogia Science* (later translated into English as the Montessori method in 1912). The Barons of Franchetti financed the publication of the book, and the methodology became known as the "Franchetti-Montessori method". Montessori's education spread to the United States by 1912 and was widely known in educational and popular publications. In 1913, Narcissa Cox Vanderlip and Frank A. Vanderlip founded the Scarborough school, the first Montessori School in the United States. However, a conflict arose between Montessori and the American educational institution. His 1914 critical treatise "The Montessori system", reviewed by education teacher William herd Kilpatrick, limited the spread of Montessori's ideas, and after 1914 they became sluggish. Montessori's Education returned to the United States in 1960 and has since spread to thousands of schools there. Montessori continued to expand his work throughout his life, developing a comprehensive model of psychological development from birth to 24 years of age, as well as educational approaches for children from 0 to 3 years of age, 3 to 6 years of age, and 6 to 12 years of age. Maria Montessori began developing her educational philosophy and methods in 1897, attending pedagogical courses at the University of Rome and studying educational theory. When visiting the Mental Hospitals of Rome while attending school with a teacher,

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Programs for infants and children Montessori classes for children under the age of three are divided into several categories, in which a number of terms are used. Nido, which means "nest" in Italian, serves a small number of children between

two months and 14 months of age, or when the child walks confidently. The "young children's community" serves more children between the ages of one and 2+ ½ or 3. Both environments emphasize materials and activities that match the size and ability of children, opportunities for movement development, and activities that promote independence. Usually the development of independence in the toilet is also highlighted. Some schools also offer "parent-infant" classes that parents attend with their very young children.

White Pine Montessori School in Moscow, Idaho, USA

Preschool and kindergarten

The Montessori classrooms for children aged 2+ ½ or 3 to 6 years are often referred to as the Montessori first school, after the Casa dei Bambini school in Rome in 1906. The normal class caters for 20 to 30 mixed-age children. provided with a fully trained leading instructor and assistants. Classrooms are usually equipped with children's sized tables and chairs individually or in small groups, with classroom materials on children's height shelves throughout the room. Much of the activities are initially provided by the teacher, after which they can be chosen more or less freely by children according to interests. The role of a teacher in the Montessori class is to provide individual guidance and advice to students by allowing each child to create their own educational path. Classroom materials generally include practical skills such as pouring and spoon making, washing, cleaning and sweeping tables. Also, materials for the development of emotions, mathematical materials, language materials, music, art and cultural materials, including "diving and swimming", magnetic and non-magnetic, more scientifically based activities such as candles and air. Activities in children's homes are usually practical, tactile materials for teaching concepts. For example, students use sanding letters to teach writing. These are letters created by cutting letters from sandpaper and placing them in wooden blocks. Children then follow these letters with their fingers to learn the shape and sound of each letter. Another example is the use of

bead chains to teach mathematical concepts, in particular multiplication. In particular, for multiples of 10, a single bead representing a single unit, a line consisting of ten beads joined representing 1×10 , and then a flat shape and Cube formed by matching 10 lines together to represent 10×10 . By matching 10 of the flats together to represent $10 \times 10 \times 10$. These materials will help to clearly understand the basic concepts on which a lot has been built in the following years

FEEDBACK AND RESULTS

Psychology Montessori in 1957 perceived the distinctive elements of human psychology that his son and partner Mario Montessori defined as "human trends". There is some debate about the specific list, but the following are clearly defined. Abstraction activity communication precision search manipulation (environment) Order orientation repetition self-perfection work (also described as "targeted activity") development "planes" Montessori observed four distinct periods or "planes" in human development, from birth to 6 years, 6 to 12 years, 12 to 18 years, and 18 to 24 years. He actively saw various features, learning techniques and developmental imperatives. this required educational approaches specific to each of the plains and to each era. The first plane lasts from birth to about six years of age. During this period, Montessori observed that the child goes through an amazing stage of physical and mental development. The child in the first plane is seen as a clear, emotional researcher and reader engaged in the developmental work of psychological self-construction and the formation of functional independence. Montessori introduced several concepts to explain the work, including absorbing intelligence, sensitive periods, and normalization.

Montessori described the behavior of a young child as the development of sensory stimuli of their environment, including the acquisition of information from senses, language, culture, and concepts with the term "swallowing intelligence". In his opinion, this force is characteristic of the first plane, and when the child is about six years old, he will fade. Montessori also observed and discovered periods of

special sensitivity to specific stimuli during this period, known as "sensitive periods". In Montessori education, the classroom environment responds to these periods, with each young child having appropriate materials and activities when periods are active. He identified the following periods and their duration. Language acquisition - interest in little things from birth to 6 years old - order from about 18 months to 3 years old - sensory fragility from birth to 4 years old about 1 to 3 years of social behavior - from about 2+ ½ to 4 years old finally, Montessori observed a psychological condition he called "normalization" in children from three to six years old. Normalization arises from the concentration and concentration of attention in an activity that serves the child's developmental needs, and is characterized by "self-discipline, continuous and happy work, social support and a feeling of empathy for others," in addition to the ability to concentrate. The second plane of development lasts from about six to twelve years. During this period, Montessori observed physical and psychological changes in children, and he developed a classroom environment, lessons, and materials to respond to these new characteristics. Physically, he observed the loss of milk teeth at the beginning of the plane and the stretching of the legs and body, and the same period of growth after it. Psychologically, he observed the "herd instinct", or tendency to work and socialize in groups, as well as the forces of intelligence and imagination. From the point of view of development, he believes that the work of a second-class child is the formation of intellectual independence, moral sense and social organization. The third plane of development includes adolescence, which is approximately twelve to eighteen years old. Montessori characterized the third plane with physical changes in puberty and adolescence as well as psychological changes. He stressed the psychological instability and difficulties in concentration at this age, as well as the development of creative trends and a "sense of justice and a sense of personal dignity". He used the term "valorization" to describe adolescents' efforts to assess their self-esteem externally. In terms of development, Montessori

believed that the work of a third straight child is to build an adult self in society. The fourth plane of development lasts from about eighteen to twenty-four years of age. Montessori wrote relatively little about this period and did not develop an educational program for age. He envisioned young people prepared on the basis of their experiences in lower-level Montessori education, ready to fully cover the study of cultures and Sciences in order to influence and lead civilization. He believed that for this age, economic independence in the form of working for money was important, and it is not necessary to arbitrarily limit the years of study at the university level, since the study of culture can continue throughout a person's life.

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